

QUALITY OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION: MODERN APPROACHES AND PROSPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article provides information on the factors ensuring the quality and efficiency of the preschool education system, their content, essence and importance, as well as ways to ensure the quality and efficiency of preschool education.

Keywords: Preschool education system, quality of education, education system, management, leadership activities, continuous education, efficiency, development, improvement, factors, mechanisms, a harmonious personality, communicativeness, cognitive.

The primary and main link of the continuous education system is the preschool education system. This education system is designed to ensure the formation of a child as a healthy, developed personality, to awaken a desire for education, and to prepare him for regular education in primary school.

The important tasks of state policy in the field of preschool education are:

- expanding the state and non-state network of preschool educational institutions:

- strengthening their material and technical base:

- providing highly qualified pedagogical personnel:

- radically increasing the coverage of children with preschool educational institutions:

- comprehensively developing children intellectually, spiritually, aesthetically, physically, as well as radically improving the quality of their preparation for school through the introduction of modern educational programs and technologies into the educational process.

Education quality management is a new paradigm of educational management in general. The idea of the quality of education continues the centuries-old traditions of ensuring the quality of human life. Understanding education as a process of forming a full-fledged personality, such an interpretation of quality is not only legitimate, but also necessary. In fact, the quality of preschool education has only

begun to be discussed and understood in the last ten years. In accordance with the State Educational Standard and the directions of preschool education, guidelines for the development of the preschool education system and requirements for its quality have been established.

Initially, pedagogical science was about education, preschool education focused on the development of the child, which, along with preparation for school and the formation of basic personal qualities, personality, ensures the maximum development of the child's creative potential, abilities and talents.

The quality of preschool education consists in organizing a pedagogical process in a kindergarten, in which the level of education and development increases in accordance with the personal, age and physical characteristics of each child in the process of upbringing. What does the quality of education in a preschool educational institution depend on? In particular, the quality of the work of the teacher, the relationships developed in the team, the conditions created by the leader for the creative search for new methods and forms of working with children, an objective assessment of the results of the activities of each employee.

In order for the preschool education quality assessment system to become a means of increasing the effectiveness of the activities of teachers, an integrated approach to its construction is necessary. Therefore, the tools for assessing the quality of education include:

- self-assessment,
- diagnostics
- monitoring or control.

The education quality assessment system monitors the quality of the educational process, the conditions and results of preschool education.

The quality of education should guarantee the services provided, meet the requirements of society, parents and children. Let us highlight the most important, in particular, internal factors that can be changed by pedagogical personnel:

- the content of education and ways of its development;
- the style of interaction between the teacher and children;
- the general organization of the life of preschool children;
- personnel, material, programmatic, methodological, financial resources;
- sanitary and hygienic conditions of the educational process and medical and health care;
- psychological support of the educational process, etc.

Along with the factors that form the quality of preschool education, the following factors also have a special importance:

- creating an educational environment;
- continuous improvement of the professional qualifications of teachers and leaders;
- a positive atmosphere in the team;
- competent, free choice of educational programs and technologies;
- a system of material incentives for the quality of labor;
- systematic collective discussion of the state of the educational process and informed acceptance of management.

The level of quality of education is not constant, it changes with the emergence of new features under the influence of external and internal factors. Therefore, it is very important to actively manage the quality of education. This can be achieved using a program-oriented approach that involves changing the educational process. A distinctive feature of a preschool educational institution as an environment for ensuring the quality of education is the continuity and stability of development. In this regard, attention should be paid to the interdependence of the processes of stabilizing the quality of education.

It is necessary to implement a specific management scheme in a preschool educational institution in the direction of stabilization - targeted development. The formation of the quality of education is significantly influenced by the organizational structure - a system of values, norms, rules, traditions. A systematic approach to interpreting and assessing the quality of preschool education as a complex multi-component system of activity implies the determination of the structural components of the quality system and the integral relationship and interaction of its constituent systems, in which cases the failure of one of the components of the preschool education quality system can lead to malfunctions in other elements of the system or systemic crises.

The development of the preschool education system is largely determined by the implementation of the latest scientific, psychological and pedagogical achievements in the field of management. One of these innovations is motivational management, based on the organization of a motivational environment.

Teachers and leaders strive to work in creative unity, which finds its place in the development of self-management systems through the participation of teachers in setting goals, determining ways and means of achieving them, optimal distribution of responsibilities and collegial solutions to emerging problems.

Quality assessment in preschool educational institutions helps to improve the educational process, promote the comprehensive development of the child, and effectively use international experience. The overall effectiveness of preschool

education can be increased by introducing modern pedagogical approaches and improving assessment systems.

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